

The Photochemical Decomposition of Acetaldehyde Solution.

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Hinshelhood and Hutchison (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1926, **111A**, 380) showed that the thermal decomposition of acetaldehyde vapour over the temperature range 430-592° is a homogeneous bimolecular gaseous reaction which follows the equation,

Berthelot and Gaudechon (*Compt. rend.*, 1913, **156**, 233) made the qualitative observation that exposed to ultra-violet radiations, acetaldehyde underwent photochemical decomposition into methane and carbon monoxide. It appeared of interest to decide experimentally whether the order of photochemical decomposition in aqueous solution is the same as that of thermal decomposition. It may be mentioned that the thermal decomposition of hydrogen iodide has been found to be bimolecular, whereas the photochemical decomposition is unimolecular. As a result of this investigation, it becomes evident that the photochemical decomposition of acetaldehyde is a unimolecular reaction, while the thermal decomposition is bimolecular.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The source of light was a quartz mercury lamp, run at constant values of current (3 amperes) and voltage (110) from a storage battery. The acetaldehyde solution was kept inside a quartz vessel whose length was 9.8 cm. and diameter 1.6 cm. The quartz vessel had two side-tubes of very thin bore and it could be filled with liquid by placing a small funnel at one tube and applying a gentle suction at the other. The reaction tube was fixed in position in the water-bath by means of a stand and was placed at a constant distance below the light source. The temperature of the mixture was kept constant by circulating water in the bath from a thermostat by means of a pump.

The acetaldehyde solution used was very dilute and the amount of it left over was estimated with iodine and bisulphite according to the method given in Sutton's "Volumetric Analysis," p. 371.

TABLE I.

Temperature of thermostat = 27.5°.

Concentration of acetaldehyde = 0.2884M.

Time,	C.c. of 0.103N-iodine ≡ 3 c.c. acetaldehyde.	<i>k</i> (unimolecular).	<i>k</i> (mean).
0 min.	16.8 c.c.	—	
180	16.1	0.0002367	0.000224
360	15.6	0.0002061	

Summary of the experimental results.

Temp. of thermostat = 27.5°.

Conc. of acetaldehyde.	<i>k</i> (unimolecular).	<i>k</i> (mean).
0.2884M	0.0002214	
0.1301M	0.0002444	0.0002296
0.0685M	0.0002342	
0.0451M	0.0002185	

It will be seen that the reaction is unimolecular and the velocity constant is independent of the initial concentration of acetaldehyde solution.

Temperature coefficient of the reaction.

Temp. of thermostat.	Conc. of acetaldehyde.	<i>k</i> (unimolecular).	<i>k</i> (mean).
37.5°	0.3264M	0.0002944	
"	0.0562M	0.0002950	0.0002947...(2)
47.5°	0.2991M	0.0003653	
"	0.0752M	0.0003791	0.0003722...(3)

Temp. coeff. = $\frac{k_2 + 10}{k_1} = 1.28$ from (1) and (2) and = 1.26 from (2) and (3).

Quantum Efficiency of the Reaction.

For determination of the quantum efficiency, the experimental arrangement was modified, by substituting a rectangular quartz vessel 2 cm. \times 2 cm. \times 8 mm., with a stopper at the top. This quartz vessel was filled with acetaldehyde solution and placed behind another large quartz vessel, 4 cm. deep, through which water was circulated. This latter served as a filter. The difference in the readings of a Moll galvanometer connected with a Moll thermopile when placed immediately behind the quartz reaction cell, (a) filled with water and (b) filled with acetaldehyde solution, gave the energy of ultra-violet radiation absorbed by the acetaldehyde solution. The energy absorbed was equivalent to 0.5 Hefner at a metre. Hence number of quanta absorbed per sec., assuming $250\mu\mu$ to be the effective radiation,

$$= \frac{4 \times 900 \times 250 \times 10^{-7} \times 0.5}{6.5 \times 10^{-27} \times 3 \times 10^{10}} = 0.23 \times 10^{15}$$

1 C.c. of acetaldehyde solution after two hours' exposure showed a diminution in strength equivalent to 0.2 c.c. of 0.06M-iodine solution. The capacity of the cell was 3 c.c.

Hence number of mols. of acetaldehyde decomposed per second

$$= \frac{3 \times 0.2 \times 0.06 \times 6.16 \times 10^{23}}{1000 \times 2 \times 60 \times 60} = 3.08 \times 10^{15}$$

$$\text{Quantum efficiency} = \frac{\text{No. of mols.}}{\text{No. of quanta}} = \frac{3.08 \times 10^{15}}{0.23 \times 10^{15}} = 13.4.$$

The value of $Nh\nu$ in this case = 120,000 calories approximately. The energy required for the decomposition of one gram molecule of acetaldehyde into methane and carbon monoxide is 3,000 cal. Hence if the whole of the absorbed energy of radiation could in some way or other be transformed into the energy of chemical transformation, we should expect a maximum quantum efficiency of 40. In the decomposition of gaseous acetaldehyde by ultra-violet light, Bowen in a preliminary investigation (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **129**, 1609) found a quantum efficiency = 2 approximately.

In aqueous solution the quantum efficiency is much larger than 2. Obviously a chain reaction is set up. The fact that there is

a definite, though small, temperature coefficient of the velocity of reaction, also supports the idea that a reaction chain is set up. We may assume the following stages:—

If the velocity of reaction (2) is small compared with the reverse reaction in (1), as is very possibly the case, the concentration of the excited molecules of acetaldehyde will be proportional to the absorbed energy of radiation. Molecular extinction coefficients of acetaldehyde in the region $280\mu\mu - 230\mu\mu$ have been determined in this laboratory and the values have been found to be very large. Hence we are justified in assuming that the whole of the incident effective radiation is absorbed by even very dilute solutions of acetaldehyde, and that the amount of energy absorbed does not vary with the concentration of the acetaldehyde solution. The velocity of reaction is therefore given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = kIC (\text{acetaldehyde}) \quad \text{from (2)}$$

where I is the intensity of incident radiation, and we obtain a unimolecular constant.

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